

Role belief system plays in shaping youth moral values in Oghara Kingdom, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research examined the role belief system plays in shaping youth moral values in Oghara Kingdom, Delta State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are: to examine if religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in Oghara Kingdom, to ascertain if ancestors punish wrong youth and reward good youth in the Oghara Kingdom, to determine if ancestors discipline those that break the law in the Oghara Kingdom and to examine if ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried out. Functional theory on religion was adopted for the theoretical frame-work for the study. In-depth interview were administered to eighteen (18) key informant, while structured and unstructured questionnaires were administered to eight hundred and twelve (812) youth. Data generated from the field were analyzed by the use of frequency, percentage and content analysis. The result revealed that youth in Oghara kingdom believe that religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the community, and that punishment by ancestors in their instructions are not carried/obeyed but the youths from the result said that ancestors do not punish and discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom. But the elders have different views on this, they claim that the youth believe the ancestors will punish wrong done by the youth and reward good done by them. That ancestor has power to harm if their instructions are not carried out. The researcher then recommends that belief system should be used to teach and discipline youth that break the law, awareness should be created to enable the youth know the negative effect of offending the ancestors.

Key words: Moral, values, Role, Youth

INTRODUCTION

In every culture the young ones (youth) are expected to abide by specified societal conduct and where they do not, such persons according to Oke (2006) are regarded as deviant. Religion and tradition of the people play paramount role in building up moral values in the lives of the youth in olden days. Kapil (2017), opined that during the Vedic (Language of the Vedas) and post Vedic period, gurukula type of education was used in impacting moral values into the lives of the youth and in doing this, the youth were expected to stay with instructor to receive instructions. According to him, people gather across the world to teach moral values to young ones and social structures are formed to provide protection to the people.

Belief systems which play great role in inculcating moral values in the life of the youth in the past seem to be reducing. According to Amos (2013), belief system instills discipline in the youth and also helps in parenting them to have good character and make them more responsible when they get to adulthood. But today we begin to see that it is no longer working especially among the youth due to what they see in the media and peer groups. Youth attention is diverted to other things presently which are affecting our society today. There is no more honesty, tolerance, hard work and integrity. If care is not taking to address this issue, the future generation will be affected badly. It is due to this that the researcher decided to carry out this research and to provide

solution to the problem of moral decadence in our society.

Specific objective of the study

The specific objective are;

- To examine if religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in Oghara kingdom,
- To ascertain if ancestors punish wrong youth and reward good youth in Oghara kingdom
- To determine if ancestors discipline those that break the law in the Oghara kingdom.
- To examine if ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried out.

Effect of Belief System on Youth Moral Values

Africans have rich cultural heritage, and every activity in African cultures revolves around religion in which they believe in Supreme Being. Hence, Buchanam (2008) opined that Religion is a strong bond that connects people and community together because it's regarded in a high esteem and it involves some artistic designs and instrument that need to be at the worship shrine. Such design and instrument according to Buchanam are mask, wooden image, drum etc which are used during worship that binds man and the spirit together (Buchanam, 2008). One of this as Buchanam stated is the worship of their ancestors which families in Africa have regard for their ancestors and it's been venerated. Family members engage in ancestral worship because they are believed to guide the family (Motsamai, 2016).

According to Swezey (1995), religion plays a great role in enriching and sustaining the ethos which nourishes the youth moral values. He also opined that religion offers moral guidance in youth upbringing, help in area of respect, moral conduct, moral purpose of doing things and the moral knowledge in religion help youth to live in the community they belong. Bewaj (2004) opined that religion determines one's action, shape society, instill moral behavior, bring social bonding, reduce stress, reduce risky lifestyle and promote unity.

Role of belief system on moral values

What people believe have a way of shaping their moral values. According to Ebhomielen(2017), Africans have rich cultural heritage, one of which is the worship of their ancestors which they reverend as supernatural being and its community base principle is that the ancestors see everywhere. Ancestors are forefathers who have died and being deified due to the good life they lived on earth (Zulu, 2002, Ezenweke, 2017 and Ukwamedua, 2018). Africans praise them, remember them, celebrate them and even pray through them and other supreme beings like god of the sky, and spirits (Zulu, 2002 Ezenweke, 2017 and Ukwamedua, 2018).

Motsamai (2016) and Ezenweke (2017) affirmed that family members engage in ancestral worship because they believe that it protects the members of the families, guide, brings favour and misfortune, especially if he's offended or people fail in their responsibilities .According to Ebhomielen (2017), ancestors communicate through priest, dream and other means and there are rituals, rites and taboos being given to them or avoid for them and all these instill fear in the heart of the youth in the community.

Role of the ancestors in African communities is enormous; Anderson (1993) and Ebhomielen (2017) listed the following roles ancestors play in shaping the moral values of the people in African communities.

1. They protect the clan from war, diseases, evil, enemies and serve as guardian of the community moral values.
2. Families are united due to their presence. They also inspire rewards, bless and empower families and it's used to convey moral values to youth.
3. It is the duty of the ancestors to link between divinity and people and also enforce discipline to prevent breaking of social values.
4. They look after their descendants which they left physically to care for their wellbeing,

help them and grant them healing whenever they are sick.

5. They have power to harm if their instructions are not carried out or if they break their rules, automatic punishment comes with it.

Apart from these listed above; they strengthen and stabilize family that would have torn apart due to the moral guidelines they provide (Allen, 2009). Beit-Hallami (2018) asserted that there is a high regard the people have for their ancestors, and it is believed that they bring happiness and good wellbeing to them including good relationship with other people. He stressed further that the youth are protected from delinquent behavior such as suicide, fornication, crime etc. and shape their moral behavior. Youth who are committed to the worship are very optimistic concerning their future, very hard working and have better relationship with their parents (Ebstyn and Furrow, 2004 and Ranald, 2015).

Discipline of offender of ancestors

The Urhobos believe that the ancestors are the guardians of morality and always ready to punish every act of immorality serve as a means of social control generally on the citizens and the youth in particular. Ekeh (2005) explained that ancestors are with the living, and are regarded as the supreme guardians of morality. To buttress this point Urhobo (2020) affirmed that it is ancestors who ensure that the solidarity of the family unit is not jeopardized by any of their children, hence insubordination and recalcitrance as Eke stressed are frowned upon by the elders, act of incest, adultery, stealing and witchcraft are all visited with punishment from the ancestors and it is believed that the living-dead (ancestors) have power to punish the nefarious men and to bless, preserve and sustain the family in a healthy state.

Theoretical Framework

Functional theory on religion was adopted for the theoretical frame work for the study. The idea of this theory can be a valuable way to understand how belief system can shape youth moral values. This

theory explains how one believes gives meaning to one's life.

Functional theory on religion by Max Weber was used in this study. It talks about the important of religion and the role it plays in shaping society. According to Devanshu (2011), religion provides certain code of conduct and behaviour that individual is expected to follow. He opined that there is connection between religion and social change, and that belief system inspired movements which have produced dramatic social change. William (n.d) viewed religion/ belief system in terms of relationship and pointed out the following; that belief has several wide range variety of super natural power, there are varieties of charismatic change, this is being expressed through symbols, people respond to it in different forms.

There are different ways of relationships which is determined by the patterned behaviour that the people of the community have put on ground. William asserted that societies made greater moral principle demands upon their gods which improved values and increase political order. He opined that people's behaviour over time religiously make known distinguished of ethics part of model.

This theory is applicable to religion/belief system and morality in contemporary African culture. It is justifiable in influencing social growth. It's also a fruitful theory in producing more research work.

Methodology

Research Design

Cross sectional study design subsumed in the survey research design was used in this research. A combination of self-constructed questionnaires which include open ended and close ended, while interview guide were used for the qualitative part to generate data.

Population of the study

The Oghara Kindom population according to the 2022 approximates population and housing census was 180,000 persons. Youth of 16-35 years living in Oghara Kingdom were focused on sample size.

Bourley formula as explained by Yamane 1978 in Ovwigho, Emuh and Idoge (2006), was used to determine the sample size.

The formula is given as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1N(e^2)}$$

Where

n is sample size

N is total population

e is tolerable error or error margin (normally 5% but in this study 3.5% was considered in order to have considerable sample size)

$$\text{therefore sample size } n = \frac{180000}{1+180000(e^2)}$$

$$n=812$$

Therefore, the sample size for the study was eight hundred and twelve (812) persons structured questionnaires and eighteen (18) persons for qualitative analysis.

Sampling Techniques

Oghara consists of two sub clan; Oghareki (bigger) and Ogharefe. Multistage sampling procedure was used, nine villages was sampled using simple random sampling method. Four villages from Ogharefe and five from Oghareki because Oghareki is bigger. Equal number (90) of respondent was purposively sampled for the selected villages while one of the communities got 92 respondents to obtain the sample size of 812 suggested for the study. Two key informants was selected using purposive sampling and interview in each of the nine sample villages to give eighteen (18) key informants that was used for in-depth interview

Instrument and method of data collection

Questionnaire survey and interview survey which consisted of both qualitative and quantitative methods was used to get detailed information on the topic under study. Secondary data was also sourced for which was obtained from literature review. Before the research was carried out by the researcher, the head of the men and women in each of the villages was informed on when to come for the interview.

Data Analysis

The researcher used quantitative data that involved the use of descriptive statistical analysis that was mainly tables which consists of frequency and percentages. The qualitative data began by immersing in the raw data, listening to tape that was used in recording severally to ensure proper transcription. The brush strokes were read multiple times, looked up the notes and listed the topics. The theme was coded after identifying it as was analyzed using manual content analysis.

Result and discussion

Table 1: Response on if religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the Oghara kingdom.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	68	8.5
Disagree	38	4.8
Agree	290	36.4
Strongly Agree	354	44.5
NR	46	5.8
Total	796	100

Source: Researcher's fieldwork computation 2024

The result of table 1 revealed that out of the seven hundred and ninety six (796) responses 68(8.5%) strongly disagree that religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the Oghara kingdom, 38(4.8%) disagree that religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the Oghara kingdom, 290(36.4%) agree that religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the Oghara kingdom, 354(44.5%) strongly agree that religious beliefs have effect on youth behavior in the Oghara kingdom, and No respond had 46(5.8%). The result revealed that the youths in Oghara kingdom believe that religious believes have effect on youth behavior in the community.

Here is the qualitative data of the respondents comments.

Religion has great effect on the youth behavior and has changed their character.

The youth believe in existence of ancestral spirit that punishes and rewarding people in the land

They believe that when they break the law the ancestor will punish them (66 years old woman, married and 75 years old man, married from Otumara and 73 years old woman, divorce and 86 years old man, widower from Edjemuoyavwe respondents 6/8/2024).

Table 2: Response on if ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths in the Oghara kingdom

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	220	27.6
Disagree	306	38.4
Agree	158	19.8
Strongly Agree	78	9.8
NR	34	4.3
Total	796	100

Source: Researcher's fieldwork computation 2024

The result of table 2 revealed that out of the seven hundred and ninety six (796) responses 220(27.6%) strongly disagree that ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths in the Oghara kingdom, 306(38.4%) disagree that ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths in the Oghara kingdom, 158(19.8%) agree that ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths in the Oghara kingdom, 78(9.8%) strongly agree that ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths in the Oghara kingdom and 34(4.3%) did not respond. From the result, the youths in Oghara kingdom do not believe that ancestors punish wrong youths and reward good youths.

In line with the quantitative data, the qualitative data is shown below:

The youth strongly believe that ancestors will punish them if they disobey the law of the land. That is why when they steal anything like goat, fowl etc and the owner wants to swear with the ancestors, they quickly drop it so that the curse/swear will not affect or kill them. This has helped youth to develop good moral values.

They believe the god of the land and ancestral spirit, that is why when you mention it to them they are very careful about it so that they will not incur the wrought of the god.

There are some care free youth who will say that ancestral spirit does not understand English. Due to that, they can do anything using English (61 years old woman, widow and 69 years old man married from Ogharefe respondents view. 6/8/2024).

Every religion has effect on anybody, likewise our ancestors. It punishes any offender.

Youth of old have deep religious belief in our ancestors. This made them to be morally upright but some of the youths of today no longer have such deep belief (61 years old woman, widow and 92 years old man, married from Ubromudu respondents 6/8/2021).

Table 3: Response on if ancestors discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	280	35.2
Disagree	212	26.6
Agree	162	20.4
Strongly Agree	140	17.6
NR	2	0.3
Total	796	100

Source: Researcher's fieldwork computation 2024

The result of table3 revealed that out of the seven hundred and ninety six (796) responses 280(35.2%)

strongly disagree that ancestors discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom, 212(26.6%) disagree that ancestors discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom, 162(20.4%) agree that ancestors discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom, 140(17.6%) strongly agree that ancestors discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom, and 2(0.3%) did not respond. The result revealed that youths in Oghara kingdom do not believe that their ancestors discipline those who break law in the Oghara kingdom.

Below is the view of the elders.

The elders strongly believe that the ancestors can punish wrong done and can also reward them. No matter how bad that youth is if it comes to the god of the land, ‘Ihwurhe’ and other idols they maintain themselves so that they will not incur the wrought of the god. They always frown at evil. (I.D.I 66 years old woman, married and 74 years old man, married from otumara and 73 years old woman, divorced and 86 years old man, widower from Edjemuoyavwe 6/8/24)

The majority of the youths believe the power behind every gods. But some stubborn ones do not care about the god of the land even if you tell them, they respond that there is nothing there (61 years old woman, married and 91 years old man from Okurode and 68 years woman, widow and 77 years old man, married from Okparode respondents. 5/8/2024).

Table 4: Response on if ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried/ obeyed

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	84	10.6
Disagree	98	12.3
Agree	384	48.2
Strongly Agree	230	28.9
Total	796	100

Source: Researcher’s fieldwork computation 2024

The result of table 4 revealed that out of the seven hundred and ninety six (796) responses 84(10.6%) strongly disagree that ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried /obeyed, 98(12.3%) disagree that ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried /obeyed, 384(48.2%) agree that ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried/ obeyed and 230(28.9%) strongly agree that ancestors have power to harm if their instructions are not carried /obeyed. The result revealed that youths in Oghara kingdom believe that ancestors have power to harm anyone if their instructions are not carried /obeyed.

The respondents in qualitative data have this to say:

Yes, they have power to harm and to kill if they are being disobeyed, that is why the youth are very careful with our ancestors. (I.D.I all the elders interviewed 5th and 6th August, 2024)

From the above data it can be deduced, that the youth

1. Believe ancestors punish evil done and reward good done

DISCUSSION

From the results of research question one it revealed that youths in Oghara kingdom believe that religious beliefs affect youth behavior in the community, and that punishment by ancestors if their instructions are not carried/ obeyed but the youths from the results said that ancestors do not punish and discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom. But the elders have a different view on this, they claim that the youth believe the ancestors will punish wrongs done by the youth and reward good done by them. The ancestors have the power to harm if their instructions are not carried out.

From the above, it is obvious that *religious/belief system can only improve the moral standard of the youth in Oghara kingdom if ancestors punish and discipline those that break law in the Oghara kingdom, and if the youths have a strong religious beliefs and recruit youth grade that are discipline.* According to Agbiji and Swart (2013) the

adolescent's moral behavior can be influenced not only by authority and peers, but also by Christian beliefs. Some teens had different views and understandings of morals. It means that the religious / belief system improves the moral standards of young people. Young people need to understand that religious beliefs and principles are important for the family, community and society of the world. Learning and learning about religion have intrinsic value as children and adolescents gain a better understanding of the diversity of society and their role in it.

Conclusion And Recommendation

The study investigated Role belief system plays in shaping youth moral values in Oghara Kingdom, Ethiopia West Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria. People have one thing or the other they believe as god in any culture which protect, provide and guide them. According to sweezey (1995), sustaining the ethos which nourishes the youth guidance in youth upbringing, help in area of respect, moral conduct, moral purpose of doing things and the moral knowledge in religion help youth to live in the community they belong. All that is needed is to strengthen belief system to shaping youth's moral behavior.

Belief system is a very important factor that shape youth moral values and behavior and promoting it can change the youth attitude towards honesty, diligence, respect, interpersonal relationship and inter-religious trust.

Based on this finding the researcher then recommends that;

1. Belief system should be used to teach and discipline youth that break the law
2. Awareness should be created to enable the youth know the negative effect of offending the ancestors.

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